

BLOCKCHAIN ECOSYSTEM FOR EDUCATION & EMPLOYMENT VERIFICATION

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ABSTRACT

Every year, millions of candidates submit their educational credentials worldwide for admissions in higher education institutes or getting a dream jobs. Their mark sheets, certificates and degree are verified in order to decide the legitimacy of their education with respect to qualification. An alarming ratio (almost 10%) of applicants, in every recruitment, fabricates their educational history or misrepresent their education in a wide variety of ways - either they overstate their academic qualifications or submit fake degrees, procured from unaccredited institutions.

The verification of necessary documents, such as educational degrees, is one of the areas where blockchain can provide tangible results. Ethereum blockchain is a concept in which a credential holder can store all his academic credentials in an encrypted format, on his own device, backed by IPFS; choosing a specific information to share with verifiers without relying on any third party or central data repository to authenticate. The system uses smart contracts and thus, no document can be shared without the explicit consent of its beholder.

Blockchain assures trust and ensures authentic data exchange, without storing any kind of verified credential on the system. The blockchain ledger, being irreversible and immutable, does not delete the original version and hence no alteration is possible.

KEYWORDS

Blockchain, Cryptography, Decentralized Applications, Data Portability, Decentralized Public Key Infrastructure, Enrolment, Ethereum, Hash function, Hashgraph, Identity Management System, IPFS, Private Key, Public Key, Self-Sovereign Identity, Validation, Zero Knowledge Proof.

1. INTRODUCTION

The grade sheets, diplomas and certificates, issued by universities and other education institutions, are considered as benchmarks of educational qualification. It has been observed that a hoard of candidates fabricate their credentials to pose themselves as a good fit. India produces an average of 2 to 2.5 million graduates a year. With such an enormous flux of degree holders, alongside unethical practices like fake degrees, and that too from unauthorized institutions, it becomes necessary to have a strict verification process. Eventually, a large number of applicants face inordinate delays in process, to get their confirmation letters.

Existing Verification process

In the current verification process:

- Schools (Colleges and Universities) usually conduct manual verification through their in-house staff.
- The verification process usually takes one to two weeks but for graduates who have passed out years ago, it stretches a little longer.

- Some schools ask for candidate's disclosure and release form before embarking on the verification.
- In case of female candidates, who write their married name, it has to be ensured that the information submitted reflects their maiden name with which they graduated.
- It is difficult to verify degrees and certificates of those universities, which do not appear as authorized entities on UGC Scroll.

2. METHODOLOGY

The present study investigates the feasibility, challenges, benefits and risks of blockchain technology in authentication of education and employment. It aims to standardize and scale-up the process of issue, third-party access and verification of credentials.

The present study is based on qualitative research methods that explores the applicability of blockchain based digital ecosystem in issuance and validation of academic credentials.

3. BLOCKCHAIN - A PANACEA

Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT), commonly known as Blockchain, refers to the technology working on decentralized databanks that provide control over the storing and sharing of data between entities, through a P2P (peer-to-peer) network, where consensus algorithms enable replication across the nodes of the network. In digital verification, blockchain ensures a flexible framework, through Hyperledger Fabric [1], with support for channels, since the secretarial models vary to a great extent.

The units, where information gets registered are blocks, similar to the pages of a ledger. Each block contains hashed information. Hash function represents a mathematical algorithm that transforms information bit to a string of alphanumeric code. Unique in itself, the hash signifies whether the information of input and output is same. Hash functions have a high avalanche effect i.e. a small change in the input string results in a different output string. This makes it almost impossible to reverse engineer unless advanced machine learning algorithms are applied [2].

In a distributed ledger, each entity of the block in the network, has same source of truth, about the validity of credentials, and the information about the attesting authority also, without getting hold of the actual degree or certificate. Leveraging blockchain technology for e-Verification, three different player – credential holders, issuers and verifiers, perform their roles.

The issuer is an academic institution that has been authorized to issue educational credentials to a candidate who so ever has fulfilled the criteria to the award of such diploma or degree (credential holder). The issuer ultimately acts as an attestation authority that stamps the validity at the time of issuing a credential. The credential holder can store these credentials in their PI wallet and utilize them to prove his qualification to the third party on demand.

The third party or the verifier, which could be a university or higher education institution or an employer, determines the validity of proof through the validity of attestation and the reliability of attesting party. It does not probe into the validity of the actual data provided in the proof.

It is a Zero Knowledge Proof authentication method, by which one entity through encryption, masks details of information received, yet proves to another entity that it has the concerned information, without having to disclose any of the actual information, to the other, to support that proof. The verification entity, despite zero knowledge, gets convinced of its validity about the information supporting the proof [3].

Thus, blockchain helps to build trust between the parties and ensures authentic data exchange, without loading any kind of verified credential on the system. The blockchain ledger is irreversible and irrevocable, and no alteration is possible as it does not delete the original transaction.

message. The second is encryption, where only the paired private key holder can decrypt the message encrypted with the public key. This process is called cryptography.

Once paired with a decentralized identity, credential holder can present the verified identifier in the form of a QR code to establish their identity and make access to certain services. The third party verifies the credential by verifying the proof of control or ownership of the forwarded attestation - the attestation had been linked with a DID and the user signs the presentation with the private key belonging to that DID. If they match, access is granted [4].

4. PROPOSED ISSUE PROCESS

In general, a university diploma or degree carries very little information like name of the awarding institution, name of the awardee, title of degree, signature of the issuing authority and the date on which issued. This could be published on a blockchain either in text format, (to create a public database) or as a hash of the digital certificate awarded to the student (to make it secure). On a blockchain, a text or hash of the certificate can be traded directly. It could be a grade sheet or a school leaving certificate. Thus, credentials could be transferred from one entity to another, as a token on the blockchain.

Fig - 2: Enrolment Process

But in certain cases, these diplomas or degrees carry auxiliary information like level of the qualification; details of the concerned higher education system; the curriculum and results

achieved; etc. that runs into several pages, and such magnitude of information cannot be posted directly on blockchain. In such cases, supplementary information may be stored off the chain and a hyperlink may be provided with the main text. This is how, a database can be constructed where some information would be held in private wallet of the user, while some other information may be held in public domain on a blockchain. Else, if the entire information is stored on blockchain, the chain would grow enormously, which may lead to high resource consumption.

For instance, a university decides to make use of blockchain technology. First of all, each student will have to register himself using his personal information such as name, address, email ID, date of birth, Aadhaar number, PAN card, education details and biometrics. The student will submit the hash of his biometric as well as that of a unique phrase. The hash of the secret phrase will be stored on the blockchain in the form of a transaction. The student will also retain a copy of this hash.

Now, the university will issue a digitally signed degree certificate to the student using its (issuer's) private key. This signed certificate will be encrypted and uploaded on the IPFS server. For this, the university authority will convert the document content into one-way hash code using cryptography. The one-way hash code, resembles the copy of the document, as a fixed length hash value or a string. The string of code acts as a key for the document. The code, now stored as a transaction in blockchain (as shown in Fig -2), is validated by the members in the blockchain. Once it is trusted as valid transaction, new blocks will be added to it. Acceptance or rejection is done using consensus algorithm [5]. The consensus algorithm may be chosen based on number of nodes, and transactions. The system will generate a relevant QR code and inquiry string code to affix in the hardcopy certificate [6].

5. VERIFICATION PROCESS

Fig - 3: Verification Process

When the user presents this document elsewhere, the code remains same as stored in the blockchain. The immutable ledger, would not only store the hash of the certificate in digital form [7] but will also authenticate the certificate, whenever required. If a student wants to take

admission in another college, he will submit the hash of his finger prints or other biometrics and that of the secret phrase. The verifying college will retrieve the hash stored on the blockchain. They will compare the hash of the student's secret phrase with the hash stored on the blockchain. If a match is found, the student's credentials are valid (Fig - 3).

5.1 Two-layer Encryption

In order to make it more secure, there can be two layers of encryption on the hash generated after uploading the credential on IPFS. The first layer of encryption will be implemented by using the public key of the holder (student) on top of which, encryption will be implemented using the private key of the issuer (authority). To validate the shared credential, decryption using the public key of the issuer will be done [8].

Fig - 4: Two-Layer Encryption Model

The resulting encrypted hash can be compared with the one available on issuer's database. If both match, the credentials will be considered as valid.

5.2 Learner's Dashboard

Though a number of universities and institutions offer massive open online courses yet they do not become very popular because of third-party certification. Since, these certifications are not publicly recognized, hence create problems in higher education or jobs. Further, if the original certificate is lost, it's a tedious task to obtain its duplicate one. Thus, encrypted digital certificates can be issued to the students, using blockchain. This will reduce the hardware costs too. By recording all completed courses on blocks, with time stamping, a learner's history can be preserved in a chronological sequence [9].

5.3 Student's Assessment

The certificate of a learner's achievements does not carry any information on curriculum or teaching-learning modalities. This deprives a student to transfer his learning achievements from one platform to another. Using blockchain technology, new instruments can be evolved to enhance the learning process and measure its outcome. By providing a learning dashboard for individual student to submit his class work and assignment through his unique ID, employing smart contracts between teachers and students, a detailed record of curriculum, teaching, learning and evaluation can be maintained [10], [11].

5.4 Track Record of Employment

Employers can verify the digital certificates instantly without contacting previous employers. Assume that a recruiter is in need of hiring a graduate and he requests for certificates from latter for verification. When a credential holder (candidate) presents a document, the technology converts or encodes the document into a cryptographic digest or hash. Submitting the same document more than once, for verification, will have the hash and the transaction markers match each time. If the document contains any alterations, the markers won't match.

Another way is to check the transaction record of the blockchain to verify the existence of a time-stamped document. Returning to the verification page of the original time-stamped document also verifies its existence. Thus, the existence of a time-stamped document on a prior date gets proven.

This will help banks, educational institutions and healthcare industries validate documents in very less time, cost, and effort.

Advantages of Blockchain based Verification

Fig. 8: The blockchain Ledger is Personal & Private

In the given milieu, Blockchain technology offers the following advantages:

1. In a decentralized structure, credentials are usually stored straight on the user's device or securely held in private repositories.
2. Decentralized Public Key Infrastructure enables everyone to create or anchor asymmetric cryptographic keys on the blockchain platform in a chronological order.
3. Educational credentials anchored on blockchain are immanently safer than those stored on centralized servers. With Ethereum blockchain, alongside a content based storage system (CBS or IPFS), it is likely to distribute the prevailing centralized data storage systems while still maintaining trust and data integrity.
4. It makes the information interoperable, protects the credential holder from being locked at one platform, allows the holder to employ data on multiple platforms and enables him to use the information for different purposes.
5. With DIDs and verifiable credentials, it is likely to transfer credentials that were anchored on one target system to another with ease.
6. Automated document verification will allow institutions to operate more professionally, by decreasing the effort, time and cost, than that required to verify the documents manually.
7. In order to ensure trustworthiness of the system, credentials once issued, cannot be changed. However, minor typological errors and certain attributes, such as house address, telephone number, etc. can change over time. Therefore, when attributes change, a new credential needs to be issued and the old one needs to be declared invalid. Blockchain registries contain the status of each credential, whether it has been revoked or updated, and if the credential is still valid.
8. The credential owner will have the power to allow or deny any organization or individual from viewing the document.
9. With current document management system, if a holder misplaces his credentials, he would have to transact with the concerned institution and have to wait until a duplicate one is issued. In the proposed system, each user will store his credentials on a digital wallet or IPFS, globally connected through blockchain.

6. CONCLUSIONS

Currently, student details are stored in discrete siloes, which are prone to security attacks. In the proposed system, the documents will be stored on user's personal device, making them safe from data breaches. The process of academic document storage can be decentralized and interoperable, where any organization or third party can verify anybody's academic credentials using blockchain platform. The Ethereum ensures that data stored on blockchain network is properly encrypted, and it's only the certificate owner, who can see or share his data at his will.

This will permit the credential holder to have control over third party access to his documents, facilitate him to employ data on multiple platforms, and protect him from being locked on one platform. Since it is a distributed system, there will be no single point of failure (SPOF).

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